

Massoud Rajavi, the historical leader of the Mujahedin-e Khalq (MEK Iran) has had a major role in forming the opposition against the religious dictatorship ruling in Iran. He was born in 1947 in Tabas, a town in eastern Iran, in a family of intellectuals. [Massoud Rajavi](#) attended Tehran University where he earned his degree in political science.

As an adolescent, Rajavi became acquainted with the teachings of Ayatollah Mahmoud Taleghani, a progressive cleric. He was also a supporter of the Freedom Movement of Iran, an organization that was in league with Mohammad Mossadegh, the popular Iranian prime minister who nationalized Iran's oil industry in 1951.

At various stages in the journey that has become MEK Iran's history, he has led it with integrity, courage, and steadfast belief in the ideals of that small group of young, freedom-loving university students and intellectuals, who formed the only Muslim revolutionary movement in Iranian history, committed to guiding the nation to a free, democratic, and progressive future.

On July 29, 1981, Massoud Rajavi announced the formation of the [National Council of Resistance of Iran \(NCRI\)](#). He invited all democratic forces opposed to religious despotism to join the democratic alternative to the religious, terrorist dictatorship. The National Council of Resistance of Iran (NCRI) has also adopted a number of plans for Iran's future, including: The NCRI's Peace Plan, the Plan for the Autonomy of Iranian Kurdistan, the Declaration on the Relations of the Provisional Government with Religion and Denominations, and the Plan on Rights and Freedoms of Women. Massoud Rajavi's unrelenting endeavors have earned him a place in Iran's history, alongside other great and respected Iranian political leaders.